

BENEFIT – SACRIFICE EFFECT ANALYSIS ON SATISFACTION, REUSE INTENTIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS FOR MOBILE APPS-BASED ONLINE OJEK SERVICES

IKHWAN TAUHID and INDAH TRI NOVITA²

^{1,2}Universitas Indonesia.

Abstract

Online Ojek Application Service is becoming a phenomenon in Indonesia. The first pioneer of this service, Gojek, gained high user growth after launching mobile apps in 2015. Here researchers wanted to understand what benefits and sacrifice people use and recommend mobile apps for Ojek Online services. Research on mobile apps was still limited. This reason was where the author wanted to complete the research on mobile apps, which then at the same time answered the phenomenon of Ojek online. The author adopted a framework (xu et al., 2015) to see what value (Benefit and sacrifice) influences satisfaction, reusing apps, intention to recommend, and level of customer recommendation. This study showed that the main factor of reuse and the recommendation of online motorcycle taxi applications was not each benefit and sacrifice separately, but was a unity of evaluation of all benefit and sacrifice factors that made up consumer satisfaction. Price perception had the greatest significant influence that affected satisfaction and was followed by hedonic and utilitarian benefits. This result answered the high level of use and recommendations that exist today.

Keyword: Mobile Apps, Aplikasi Ojek Online, Kepuasan, Apps Continuance Intention, Benefit Sacrifice, Rekomendasi

INTRODUCTION

Gojek was established in 2011; at the beginning of its establishment, Gojek could only be ordered by phone to the call center, and the number of existing drivers only amounts to 20. In 2014, the founder Nadiem Makarim received an investment offer from investors for Gojek, which amounted to a considerable amount. Finally, in 2015, Gojek launched its Smartphone application and was a pioneer in the Ojek transportation application. Then in March, it was even downloaded by more than 132,000 users with a total of 3700 drivers.

Seeing the extraordinary growth of Gojek, GrabTaxi, a taxi booking company through an application originating from Malaysia, was interested in expanding the ojek transportation business via the Smartphone application by launching the GrabBike application in May 2015. To face Gojek as a first mover, GrabBike offered a very low promo price to attract customers, which was Rp.5000 anywhere. It made Gojek make the same promo price offer which was as big as Rp.10, 000, to deal with the emergence of GrabBike, which was quite aggressive.

After Gojek's services expanded and were known everywhere, there were competitors of online motorcycle taxi services such as Grabbike, Bluejek, Ladijek, Ojesy, and other online motorcycle taxi services. Gojek and Grabbike dominate to be the customer's top choice of all these online motorcycle taxi services. The use of mobile apps as a medium for booking Gojek transportation services increases the demand for Gojek services. When Gojek was still using

phones and SMS to book their services, there were very few requests. Therefore, here is something interesting to research, where mobile apps can affect the adoption rate and recommendations of Gojek services.

Research and research on the adoption of mobile apps are still very rare. Most of this research uses the Reference Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis et al., 1989) as a research model and framework. TAM is already used extensively as a research base for adopting computer and Information Systems devices. However, this TAM model focuses on adoption for traditional technologies such as computers and on the use to do office work or arguably user technology where companies carry out the cost of technology adoption.

Kim et al., 2007 propogandized the theory of adopting a technology they named the value-based adoption model for mobile internet users. Here they argue that mobile internet users are people who have a dual role, namely as technology users and service consumers. Individuals carry out the cost for technology adoption to propogandize the use of value consisting of benefits and sacrifices (costs) for technology adoption. Then (Xu et al., 2015) propogandized adoption models and recommendations specifically for mobile apps. Here they use the Value-satisfaction-loyalty framework to determine the adoption and recommendations for mobile apps. The interesting thing about their research is that they reduce the value variables to benefit variables and separate sacrifice to better know the specifics of the effect of each benefit-sacrifice variable on the intention of using continuous apps, the intention to recommend, and the level of recommendation itself.

The formulation of this research problem is to find what value (benefit and sacrifice) causes the high demand for online motorcycle taxi services and the level of their recommendation to use the online motorcycle taxi service. These value glasses (benefit and sacrifice) are also used to answer the common question in the community. Whether online motorcycle taxi transportation services such as Gojek, Grabbike, etc., will continue to be used if the promotional price of online motorcycle taxi transportation services of Rp.15, 000 no longer exists. Consumers go through three stages in consuming goods and services from the beginning before buying to stop using the product or service. The three stages of the consumption process include Pre-purchase Issue, Purchase Issue, and Post-Purchase Issue. This stage is where the role of consumer behavior is needed so that marketers can know their behavior and carry out the right strategies to sell products or services.

People consume goods and services due to needs and wants. These needs can be in the form of utilitarian needs, namely the desire to get functional and practical benefits, usually objectively based on tangible attributes of a product. Hedonic benefits are the need for experience, emotion, and fantasy, usually to meet excitement and confidence. The last desired condition is the consumer's goal. Marketers create products and services that provide the expected benefits and help consumers reduce pressure to get what is needed.

In (Lin et al. 2012) developed a framework based on the value-based adoption model (Kim et al., 2007) and the Technology Acceptance Model (Davis et al., 1989). Compared to other literature, they use benefits not based on utilitarian-hedonic or functional-recreational but based

on research on IPTV, where benefits are defined as advantages offered by IPTV. As for sacrifice, they use monetary-non monetary sacrifice based (Kim et al. 2007) coupled with knowledge of alternatives and change of viewing habits. They use the framework to find out the continuance intention of IPTV. In contrast to some of the literature described earlier, Kim et al., 2015 developed the benefit-cost model without using value or perceived value. Here they reduce the value as a separate variable to determine the significance of each benefit and sacrifice's effect on app continuance, intention to recommend, and recommendation. Their benefit variables use utilitarian and hedonic benefits, and their sacrifice variables use monetary and non-monetary sacrifice.

METHOD

➤ Research Framework

This research was based on a framework (Xu et al., 2015). The researcher developed a research model using a value-satisfaction-loyalty framework to be applied to adoption and mobile application recommendations. Here the researcher also reduced value into benefits and separated sacrifices so that benefit-sacrifice became antecedent directly from Satisfaction, Apps continuance interface, Intention to recommend. Here researchers tried to see the influence of each perceived value on satisfaction, app continuance intention, and intention to recommend.

Figure 1. Research Framework

1. Hypothesis

Based on the model and framework of the research, hypotheses were carried out regarding the following research:

- H1: Utilitarian Benefit positively affects satisfaction
- H2: Hedonic Benefit positively affects satisfaction
- H3: Non-monetary Sacrifice negatively affects satisfaction
- H4: Perceived Price positively affects satisfaction
- H5: Utilitarian Benefit positively affects Apps continuance intention

- H6: Hedonic Benefit positively affects Apps continuance intention
- H7: Perceived Price positively affects Apps continuance intention
- H8: Non-monetary Sacrifice negatively affects Apps continuance intention
- H9: Utilitarian Benefit positively affects intention to recommend
- H10: Hedonic Benefit positively affects intention to recommend
- H11: Perceived Price positively affects intention to recommend
- H12: Non-monetary Sacrifice negatively affects intention to recommend
- H13: Satisfaction positively affects continuance intention apps
- H14: continuance intention apps positively affect intention to recommend
- H15: Intention to recommend has a positive effect on recommendation

2. Research Design

The research used descriptive quantitative methods to test a research framework developed by Xu et al., 2015 on the mobile apps-based online motorcycle taxi service industry.

3. Number of Research Samples

This research was conducted on the consumer population who had downloaded the online motorcycle taxi service application as of Dec 16th, 2015, with a population of 6.1 million downloads. It was assumed that all application downloads had already used the online motorcycle taxi service services. To determine the number of samples, researchers refer to Hair et al., 2007 where the number of samples if using the SEM maximum likelihood analysis method was five times the number of observed variables or indicators, in which case there were 49 indicators. So that the number of samples that researchers must obtain was 245 respondents.

4. Sample Retrieval Method

This study used convenience sampling methods through online-based questionnaire surveys and questionnaire surveys printed. Before being disseminated, preliminary testing of the questionnaire was to be distributed. After that, the dissemination of preliminary testing questionnaires (Pre-test) was carried out to 35 people. The main questionnaire was then distributed online and through a printed questionnaire with a convenience sampling method on April 17-30, 2016. The spread of online questionnaires was carried out using typeform.com services to conduct online surveys. The spread of printed questionnaires was carried out by researchers on the campus environment of the University of Indonesia, located in Salemba.

5. Data Analysis Methods

This research itself used Structural Equation Modeling using the LISREL 8.51 tool. SEM research was facilitated so that there is no need to do repeated multiple regressions for fairly complex equation models. The first analysis was the analysis of the measurement model. This analysis was to test the validity and reliability of the measurement model. The second analysis

was structural model analysis. This analysis tested the level of significance of the coefficient that the estimation performed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Of the total 287 respondents who entered both online and printed questionnaires, it was found that 81% of respondents used GO-JEK, and 19% used GrabBike.

Figure 2. Apps that respondents use

From the data obtained, 53% of respondents were aged 26-35 years, and 34% of respondents were aged 18-25 years. This means that 87% of respondents were millennials.

Figure 3. Age of Respondents

Of the respondents, 52% were men, and 48% were women.

Figure 4. Respondent Gender

The majority of S1-educated respondents were 80%, followed by S2 respondents 14%.

Figure 5. Respondent's Last Education

From the data, the respondent's monthly expenditure was quite equal where 30% of respondents had expenditures between Rp.1 million to 3 million, then 26% of respondents had an expenditure of Rp.5 million to Rp. 10 million.

Figure 6. Respondents' monthly expenses

A total of 42% had private employee jobs, and 28% of respondents were the remaining students spread among civil servants, STATE-OWNED employees, etc.

Figure 7. Respondent's Job

38% of respondents were heavyweight users of online motorcycle taxis with a usage frequency per month above 15 times, and 32% were casual users with a frequency of use per month between 2 to 6 times.

Figure 8. Frequency of respondents using online motorcycle taxis

The majority of respondents (68%) used the internet for more than 3 hours, followed by 16% for 2 to 3 hours.

Figure 9. Frequency of using the internet

Figure 10. T-Values of Confirmatory Factor Analysis

From the Confirmatory Factor Analysis test results, all latent variables and observed variables/indicators met the requirements of validity and reliability. In addition, when viewed

from the model's overall fittest, the model obtained a good Goodness of Fit where RMSEA < 0.8, so there was no need to re-specify the model. This model was also in line with the results of pre-tests that had been run before, in which the data from this measurement model was valid and reliable.

After processing using Lisrel 8.51, it showed that this study met the Absolute Fit Measure requirement where the RMSEA value was 0.051, which means it qualifies for the RMSEA value match rate. As for the incremental fit measure size, three GOF meet the matched level requirements, including NNFI, IFI, and CFI, which had a value of > 0.9. After knowing the size of the model match from this study, a structural equation test was carried out where it was necessary to see the significance of the influence of a latent variable on another latent variable. From this, we could see and also analyze the influence between variables.

Table 1: The causal relationship between latent variables

No	The influence between latent variables	t-value	Description
1	Utilitarian Benefit → Satisfaction	2,42	Significant
2	Hedonic Benefit → Satisfaction	2,75	Significant
3	Non-Monetary Sacrifice → Satisfaction	-0,89	Insignificant
4	Perceived Price → Satisfaction	5,39	Significant
5	Utilitarian Benefit → Apps Continuance Intention	0,77	Insignificant
6	Hedonic Benefit → Apps Continuance Intention	0,71	Insignificant
7	Non-Monetary Sacrifice → Apps Continuance Intention	-0,89	Insignificant
8	Perceived Price → Apps Continuance Intention	0,69	Insignificant
9	Utilitarian Benefit → Intention to Recommend	0,77	Insignificant
10	Hedonic Benefit → Intention to Recommend	-1,6	Insignificant
11	Non-Monetary Sacrifice → Intention to Recommend	1,73	Insignificant
12	Perceived Price → Intention to Recommend	-0,12	Insignificant
13	Satisfaction → Apps Continuance Intention	5,67	Significant
14	Satisfaction → Intention to recommend	1,83	Insignificant
15	Apps Continuance Intention → Intention to Recommend	5,25	Significant
16	Intention to → Recommendation recommend	7,12	Significant

As shown in the table, of the 16 causal relationships between latent variables tested in the study, only six causal relationships had a significant influence because the t-value value was > 1.96 or < -1.96. The other ten causal relationships did not have a significant influence. The results of the hypothesis analysis can be seen in the following table.

Table 2. Hypothesis Analysis

No	Hypothesis	Hypothesis Statement	t-value	Description
1	H1	Utilitarian Benefit has a positive effect on satisfaction	2,42	Hypothesis Accepted
2	H2	Hedonic Benefit has a positive effect on satisfaction	2,75	Hypothesis Accepted
3	H3	Non-monetary sacrifice negatively affects satisfaction.	-0,89	Hypothesis Rejected
4	H4	Perceived Price has a positive effect on satisfaction	5,39	Hypothesis Accepted
5	H5	Utilitarian Benefit positively affects Apps continuance intention	1,44	Hypothesis Rejected
6	H6	Hedonic Benefit positively affects Apps continuance intention.	-0,71	Hypothesis Rejected
7	H7	Perceived Price positively affects Apps continuance intention	0,69	Hypothesis Rejected
8	H8	Non-monetary sacrifice negatively affects Apps continuance intention.	-0,89	Hypothesis Rejected
9	H9	Utilitarian Benefit positively affects intention to recommend	0,77	Hypothesis Rejected
10	H10	Hedonic benefit positively affects intention to recommend	-1,6	Hypothesis Rejected
11	H11	Perceived Price positively affects intention to recommend	-0,12	Hypothesis Rejected
12	H12	Non-monetary sacrifice negatively affects intention to recommend	1,73	Hypothesis Rejected
13	H13	Satisfaction has a positive effect on continuance intention apps	5,67	Hypothesis Accepted
14	H14	Satisfaction has a positive effect on the intention to recommend	1,83	Hypothesis Rejected
15	H15	Apps continuance intention positively affects intention to recommend	5,25	Hypothesis Accepted
16	H16	Intention to recommend has a positive effect on recommendation	7,12	Hypothesis Accepted

From the results of the causal relationship test obtained from a total of 16 hypotheses submitted by researchers, only six hypotheses were accepted while the other ten hypotheses were rejected. Here it can be seen that latent variables such as Utilitarian Benefit, Hedonic Benefit, Non-Monetary Sacrifice, and Perceived Price do not directly influence Continuance Intention and Intention to Recommend Apps but have an indirect influence first through mediation variables such as Satisfaction and Apps Continuance Intention. Based on the causality relationship test results, here are some things that can explain why some of these hypotheses can be rejected and accepted.

Figure 11. Influence of each variable

Based on the framework developed by Xu et al., 2015 obtained quite interesting results. It turns out that the benefit and sacrifice variables directly influence satisfaction without having to be mediated first through perceived value variables. Of the four variables, namely Utilitarian Benefit, Hedonic Benefit, Non-monetary sacrifice, and perceived price, only three variables

have a significant influence on satisfaction and only one that does not have a significant influence, namely non-monetary sacrifice variables.

Table 3. Effect of Benefit-Sacrifice on satisfaction

No	Influence influence	Influence influence
1	Utilitarian Benefit → Satisfaction	Positive effect
2	Hedonic Benefit → Satisfaction	Positive effect
3	Non-monetary sacrifice → Satisfaction	No effect
4	Perceived Price → Satisfaction	Positive effect

Of the four variables, perceived price variables have the greatest significant influence compared to other variables. These results show that the price factor is the thing that most affects consumer satisfaction in using the online motorcycle taxi application. As is known, during 2015, the price offered to consumers was quite cheap. Here the two companies that are still in the introduction phase compete to attract as many consumers as possible with the promotion of low prices. The low price offered here is well reflected in the results of this study.

After gaining significant influence from the three Variables, benefit, and sacrifice, the researchers found that the Benefit and sacrifice variables did not directly influence the continuance intention and intention to recommend applications but were mediated in full by satisfaction variables. This result means that consumers must feel satisfied first with the new online motorcycle taxi application. Then they will have the intention to use the application continuously and recommend the online motorcycle taxi application. This result breaks the researcher's hypothesis that value variables that are breakdown into benefit and sacrifice variables directly influence continuance intention and intention to recommend applications.

This study also showed that satisfaction has a significant influence on Apps continuance intention, apps continuance intention has a significant effect on the intention to recommend, and intention to recommend has a direct effect on recommendations. This result shows that for consumers to recommend the online motorcycle taxi application, they must first be satisfied with the online ojek application. When satisfied, they will intend to reuse it, which leads to the intention to recommend this online motorcycle taxi application.

This research answers why online motorcycle taxi services based on mobile apps are so viral and mushrooming. It turns out that it is not because of the direct influence of each utilitarian benefit, hedonic benefit, and low price, but rather it turns out that consumers are satisfied with their overall experience using this online motorcycle taxi application. This situation causes them to have the desire to reuse this application. This desire directly also makes them have the intention to recommend it to the people around them. The hypothesis that the direct influence of competing for low-priced promos causes virality or ease to order motorcycle taxis through the application makes people recommend it is not proven.

This research successfully shows that the strategy that online motorcycle taxi application companies have carried out is right, namely by providing promo prices that are quite cheap in a long enough time. Variable perceived price significantly influences satisfaction with a t-value of 5.39 compared to other benefit and sacrifice variables. Thanks to the promotion of low prices

and other benefits, the level of reuse and recommendations to use this online motorcycle taxi application are very high. Some online motorcycle taxi applications such as GO-JEK and Grab Bike have become very virally discussed by all Indonesians. This situation is very beneficial for both companies because both are still at the introduction stage because their online motorcycle taxi applications are still newly introduced to the public. Their number of users is growing so rapidly thanks to word-of-mouth that they have to prepare more drivers to serve their customers.

The two online motorcycle taxi companies currently use the competitive advantage method through the hybrid cost leadership method at low prices and differentiation through technological innovation using smartphone applications. Jay Barney proposed the VRIN framework to find out the level of sustainable competitive advantage of a company. This framework argues that resources are a source of sustainable competitive advantage judging from how valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable a company is using this framework, it can be known that online motorcycle taxi application companies have a Competitive Parity level where the resources they have are only valuable without scarcity, easily imitated, and substituted. The continuous use of promo prices, which can bring in consumers more quickly, can also accelerate the end of the company's cash flow; this can make the company not sustain for a long time. So that in the future, online motorcycle taxi application companies will no longer be able to do strategies at low prices. However, according to this research, suppose online motorcycle taxi application companies eliminate the low-price strategy. In that case, the level of satisfaction and the recommendation of using the service will be reduced, resulting in customers stopping to continue using the online motorcycle taxi application.

For this reason, in the future, online motorcycle taxi application companies must be able to make changes in strategy that initially rely on prices to attract consumers to become more utilitarian benefits and hedonic benefits. For this reason, several stages should be carried out, namely: Reducing price subsidies for discounts slowly following the customer level. Add and increase Utilitarian Benefit and Hedonic Benefit. Increase the bond with consumers.

The Hedonic benefit variable consists of two variables of first-order Aesthetic and perceived enjoyment. Improving aesthetic benefits is done by making the application design attractive to look at to help consumers more easily use the application. Then the improvement of Perceived Enjoyment can be made by understanding the route taken by the user. Here, the application can offer an alternative culinary tour on the paths passed by the user. Users, especially those not in a hurry, can stop by first to taste the existing culinary tours. Another alternative is to provide gamification based on the level of the user profile, where users who have used it several times can get general status and so on (status can be selected). This condition can be done to create excitement when becoming a customer of the online motorcycle taxi application.

The first thing that an online motorcycle taxi application should do is increase utilitarian benefits. Where this utilitarian benefit consists of Apps Utility and Apps Quality, the increase in the benefits of Apps Utility can be done by creating automatic customer profiling by studying user behavior while using the application. So that before consumers order, the application can guess the predicted route to be done by consumers without having to enter location coordinates

again, then also by entering route optimization that can predict alternative routes when stuck. The next thing includes weather predictions, so when it is predicted to rain when on the way, users are offered an alternative mode of transportation from the service, for the case of GO-JEK offered GO-CAR, while for GrabBike offered GrabCar. Furthermore, the improvement of Apps Quality benefits is to continue increasing the application's reliability so that the distance occurs interference, crashes, or slow to use.

CONCLUSIONS

Through this research, it was found that some interesting things are enough to show the behavior of Indonesian consumers towards online motorcycle taxi applications. Satisfaction is only influenced by utilitarian benefits, hedonic benefits, and perceived prices without variable non-monetary sacrifice. Variable benefits (utilitarian and hedonic) and sacrifice (non-monetary and perceived price) have no direct influence on variables' continuance intention and intention to recommend but are mediated in full by satisfaction variables. Here consumers form their level of satisfaction first and then from experiencing the experience of using an online motorcycle taxi application. If they are satisfied, they will use the apps again and recommend the apps to their friends. This situation breaks the common hypothesis spread in the community that it is the promotional price that makes people use online motorcycle taxi applications continuously and recommend them to their friends. Of the three benefit and sacrifice variables that make up the satisfaction, perceived price variables have the most significant influence compared to utilitarian and hedonic benefits. This condition shows that the low promotional prices floated by Gojek and GrabBike have a significant influence on customer satisfaction. So it can be said that the low price makes people want to reuse and recommend online motorcycle taxi applications through variable satisfaction mediation. Satisfaction has a positive effect on continuance intention apps. Apps continuance intention has a positive effect on the intention to recommend. Intention to recommend has a positive effect on the recommendation. When he already intends to recommend the service, a consumer will do their behavior to recommend this service. Recommendations themselves are a positive Word-of-Mouth from consumers to other consumers.

Through this research, online motorcycle taxi application companies can do several things to compete with competitors. Low prices have been the key success factor of online ojek application companies such as GO-JEK and GrabBike. However, implementing a low price strategy is not a sustainable strategy because one day, there will be a limited capital resource. The first thing that an online motorcycle taxi application should do is increase utilitarian benefits. The second thing is to increase the Hedonic Benefit of the app. Then the improvement of Perceived Enjoyment can be made by understanding the route taken by the user. Here, the application can offer an alternative culinary tour on the paths passed by the user. Users, especially those not in a hurry, can stop by first to taste the existing culinary tours. Online motorcycle taxi application companies should also change their customer journey to increase the bond with consumers before they make price changes to normal prices.

Due to the limitations of researchers, here are some suggestions for future research:

1. Use other non-monetary sacrifice variable indicators to measure the effects of non-monetary sacrifice on satisfaction.
2. Use brand awareness variables or associations to see their effect on loyalty or reuse intentions.
3. Make comparisons between different online motorcycle taxi applications so that it can be known the behavior of each online motorcycle taxi application consumer.

References

- Xu, Chenyan, Daniel Peak, and Victor Prybutok. "A customer value, satisfaction, and loyalty perspective of mobile application recommendations." *Decision Support Systems* 79 (2015): 171-183.
- Kim, Hee-Woong, Hock Chuan Chan, and Sumeet Gupta. "Value-based adoption of mobile internet: an empirical investigation." *Decision Support Systems* 43.1 (2007): 111-126.
- Davis, Fred D., Richard P. Bagozzi, and Paul R. Warshaw. "User acceptance of computer technology: a comparison of two theoretical models." *Management Science* 35.8 (1989): 982-1003.
- Alnawas, I. and Aburub, F., 2016. The effect of benefits generated from interacting with branded mobile apps on consumer satisfaction and purchase intentions. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 31, pp.313-322
- Yang, Zhilin, and Robin T. Peterson. "Customer perceived value, satisfaction, and loyalty: The role of switching costs." *Psychology & Marketing* 21.10 (2004): 799-822.
- Mustak, Mekhail, Elina Jaakkola, and Aino Halinen. "Customer participation and value creation: a systematic review and research implications." *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal* 23.4 (2013): 341-359.
- E. Deci, Effects of externally mediated rewards on intrinsic motivation, *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 18 (1) (1971 (Jan.)).
- B.J. Babin, W.R. Darden, M. Griffin, Work and/or fun: measuring hedonic and utilitarian shopping value, *Journal of Consumer Research* 20 (1994 (Mar.)).
- Oliver, R. L. "Measurement and Evaluation of Satisfaction Processes in Retail Settings," *Journal of Retailing* (57:3), Fall 1981, pp. 25-48
- J. Jacoby, R. Chestnut, *Brand Loyalty Measurement and Management*, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1978.
- R.L. Oliver, Whence consumer loyalty, *Journal of Marketing* 63 (special issue), 1999, pp. 33-44
- Chaudhuri, M.B. Holbrook, The chain of effects from brand trust and brand affect to brand performance: the role of brand loyalty, *Journal of Marketing* 65(2), 2001, pp. 81-93.
- Anderson, E.W. (1996), "Customer satisfaction and price tolerance," *Marketing Letters*, Vol. 7 No. 3, pp. 265-74
- Martín-Consuegra, David, Arturo Molina, and Águeda Esteban. "An integrated model of price, satisfaction, and loyalty: an empirical analysis in the service sector." *Journal of Product & Brand Management* 16.7 (2007): 459-468.
- Huber, Frank, Andreas Herrmann, and Martin Wricke. "Customer satisfaction as an antecedent of price acceptance: results of an empirical study." *Journal of Product & Brand Management* 10.3 (2001): 160-169.
- Barney, Jay. "Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage." *Journal of management* 17.1 (1991): 99-120.